

Mepazine Hydrochloride as a New Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III)

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Mepazine hydrochloride forms a red coloured complex with ruthenium(III) at room temperature in acid medium. The red complex exhibits absorption maximum at 512-516 nm. Beer's law is valid over the concentration ranges 0.40-12.8 ppm in sulphuric acid and 0.32-6.4 ppm in hydrochloric acid. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.022 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ in H_2SO_4 and 0.015 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ in HCl. The respective molar absorptivity is $4.48 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ in H_2SO_4 and $6.7 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ in HCl. The composition study by molar ratio method indicates that the ruthenium-MH complex has a ratio of 1 : 2.

THE authors reported the use of mepazine hydrochloride (MH), 10-[(1-methyl-3-piperidyl) methyl] phenothiazine hydrochloride as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium². The present work describes MH as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III). The MH forms a red coloured complex with ruthenium(III) at room temperature in sulphuric or hydrochloric acid medium. The coloured reaction has been thoroughly investigated and used for the rapid spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III).

Experimental

Apparatus: Beckman Model DB Spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm silica cells was used for all absorbance measurements.

Reagents

Standard ruthenium(III) solution:

A stock solution of ruthenium was prepared by dissolving 0.9850 g of ruthenium(III) chloride (M/s Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in dilute Analar hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1 litre to give 1M with respect to the acid. It was standardized gravimetrically by the thionalide method³. The stock solution was further diluted to give a standard solution of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Mepazine hydrochloride solution:

A 0.2% aqueous solution of MH was prepared and stored in a refrigerator.

All other chemicals and reagents used in this investigation were of analytical reagent quality.

Recommended procedure for spectrophotometric determinations.

An aliquot of the stock solution containing 8 to 320 μg of ruthenium(III) was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. 5 ml of 5M sulphuric acid or 8.5 ml of 6M hydrochloric acid and 2 ml of 0.2% MH solution were added and the volume was made up to the mark with doubly distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm after standing 10 minutes in sulphuric acid medium and 25 minutes in hydrochloric acid medium against a reagent blank prepared similarly without ruthenium. The absorbances were plotted against concentration of ruthenium. The amount of ruthenium in the sample solution was deduced from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations have shown that MH reacts with ruthenium(III) at room temperature in sulphuric or hydrochloric acid medium to form a red coloured complex. The rate of reaction and stability of the colour depend on the nature and concentration of the acid medium. Nitric acid cannot be used as reaction medium because it oxidises MH to a coloured radical.

Spectral characteristics

The absorption spectra of ruthenium, MH and

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ruthenium-MH complex are shown in Fig. 1. The complex exhibits maximum absorption at 512-516 nm in both acids. The absorption spectra of ruthenium and the reagent under similar conditions show that they do not absorb at this wavelength. All subsequent studies were carried out at 515 nm.

Figure 1. Absorption spectra of reagent blank, Ru and Ru-MH complex in HCl and H_2SO_4 media. 1. Reagent blank in $2M$ HCl; 2. Reagent blank in $1M$ H_2SO_4 ; 3. Ru in $2M$ HCl; 4. Ru in $1M$ H_2SO_4 ; 5. Ru-MH complex in $2M$ HCl and 6. Ru-MH complex in $1M$ H_2SO_4 (concentration of Ru = $4 \mu g/ml$).

Optimum acid strength

It is found that the optimum range of sulphuric acid is $0.4-1.8M$ and that of hydrochloric acid is $1.0-3.5M$ as shown by maximum intensity of colour. Below $0.4M$ sulphuric acid or $1.0M$ hydrochloric acid the development of red colour of the complex is slow and slight turbidity is observed at acid concentrations above $1.8M$ sulphuric acid or $3.5M$ hydrochloric acid. An acid strength of $1M$ sulphuric acid or $2M$ hydrochloric acid was chosen for further studies.

Rate of reaction and stability of colour

The ruthenium-MH complex is formed at room temperature and constant absorbance values are obtained 10 minutes after adding the reagent to ruthenium in sulphuric acid and 25 minutes in hydrochloric acid. The absorbance readings remain constant for 120 minutes in sulphuric acid and 90 minutes in hydrochloric acid.

Effect of varying reagent concentration

It is found that the maximum colour formation is attained when the mixture contains only eight-fold excess of the reagent (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Effect of reagent concentration on Ru-MH complex 1. $2M$ HCl medium and 2. $1M$ H_2SO_4 medium. Wavelength = 515 nm (concentration of Ru = $4 \mu g/ml$).

Sequence of addition of reagents

No change in the absorbance or colour intensity of the complex is observed if the order of addition of reactants is changed.

Effect of varying temperature

The ruthenium-MH complex obtained as recommended in the procedure has been investigated at temperatures ranging from $4-97^\circ$. The absorbance readings are constant in the temperature range $10-50^\circ$.

Adherence to Beer's law and optimum concentration

Beer's law is valid over the concentration ranges, $0.40-12.80$ ppm in sulphuric acid and $0.32-6.4$ ppm in hydrochloric acid (Fig. 3). The optimum concen-

Figure 3. Beer's law curves. 1. $2M$ HCl medium and 2. $1M$ H_2SO_4 medium; Wavelength = 515 nm.

tration range for the effective spectrophotometric determination evaluated by Ringbom's method^{5,6} is, 1.20-12.0 ppm in sulphuric acid or 1.0-6.2 ppm in hydrochloric acid.

Sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complex

For log I₀/I=0.001, the sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's law data is 0.015 μg/cm² in hydrochloric acid and 0.022 μg/cm² in sulphuric acid. The molar absorptivity for the ruthenium-MH complex is 6.7 × 10⁴ l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in hydrochloric acid and 4.48 × 10⁴ l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in sulphuric acid.

Precision and accuracy

The precision and accuracy of the method have been studied by analysing solutions containing known amounts of ruthenium ten times in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid. It can be seen from the results summarised in Table I; the errors are ±1.3%.

TABLE I—PRECISION AND ACCURACY

Experiment	Ruthenium(III), ppm Taken	Relative error %	Standard deviation, ppm	Range, ppm	
1	2.8	2.82*	+0.71	0.025	0.083
2	5.6	5.64*	+0.71	0.026	0.166
3	10.4	10.00*	-0.38	0.018	0.294
4	1.6	1.58**	-1.25	0.021	0.012
5	4.0	4.00**	0.00	0.004	0.032

* Sulphuric acid medium

** Hydrochloric acid medium.

Effect of diverse ions

The effect of anions and cations which often accompany ruthenium was studied with 4 ppm of ruthenium. The results presented in Table 2 show

TABLE 2—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF 4 PPM OF RUTHENIUM(III)

Ion added	Tolerance limit, ppm medium		Ion added	Tolerance limit, ppm medium	
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄		HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
F ⁻	1750	1825	Fe(III)	1.6	2.0
Cl ⁻	7000	7000	Co(II)	90	96
Br ⁻	2150	2415	Ni(II)	1480	1560
I ⁻	3.5	4.0	Cu(II)	350	1100
NO ₃ ⁻	725	1575	Rh(III)	14	15
PO ₄ ³⁻	1320	2050	Pd(II)	0.3	0.5
SO ₄ ²⁻	7200	10000	Ag(I)	0.3	0.5
CH ₃ COO ⁻	10850	11530	Os(VIII)	0.6	0.8
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	745	875	Ir(III)	9.5	10.0
EDTA	40	7430	Pt(IV)	1.0	2.0
			Au(III)	0.4	0.6

that the tolerance limit is higher in sulphuric acid than in hydrochloric acid medium. Large amounts of fluoride, chloride, bromide, nitrate, phosphate, sulphate, acetate, EDTA, cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), rhodium(III) and iridium(III) have no effect on the determination of ruthenium(III) while palladium(II), osmium(VIII), silver(I) and gold(III) interfere.

Composition of the ruthenium-MH complex

Composition studies by continuous variations^{5,6}, Slope ratio⁷ and logarithmic methods⁸ failed to give any definite composition owing to the interference of yellow colour of ruthenium at relatively low range of reagent concentration. However, the mole ratio method⁹ establishes a composition of 1 : 2 between the metal and reagent in both acids (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Composition of Ru-MH complex by molar ratio method. 1. Ru=MH=2.5 × 10⁻⁴M (2M HCl); 2. Ru=MH=2.5 × 10⁻⁴M (1M H₂SO₄); 3. Ru=MH=2.0 × 10⁻⁴M (2M HCl) and 4. Ru=MH=2.0 × 10⁻⁴M (1M H₂SO₄). Temp. = 27 ± 1°. Wavelength = 515 nm.

Stability constant of the complex

The apparent stability constants of the complex in 1M sulphuric acid and 2M hydrochloric acid at 27 ± 1° as evaluated by mole ratio method have log K values of 9.41 ± 0.1 and 9.28 ± 0.1 respectively.

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